

2. Relationship between grain grade of the 1st primary branch (bottom) and yield. Andhra Pradesh, India.

Main and ratoon rice crop performance in mangrove swamps

M. P. Jones, *WARDA Regional Mangrove Swamp Rice Research Station, Rokupr, Sierra Leone*

In some of the tidal mangrove swamps of Sierra Leone and Guinea, very low

yields are obtained from second crop transplanted rice because farmers prefer long-duration photoperiod-sensitive varieties. The first crop matures in late Dec or early Jan. The second crop transplanted in Jan is subject to high levels of salt in the soil or to flooding at late growth stages.

We evaluated ratoon cropping as a

Performance of 16 rice varieties grown as main and ratoon crops in mangrove swamps in Rokupr, Sierra Leone.

Variety	Salt tolerance ratio	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		Growth duration (d)	
		Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
High tolerance					
Pa Foday Yoreh 260	0.69	2.7 ab	1.7 a	194	90
Pa Merr 108A	0.68	2.1 bc	0.9 c	197	94
Pa Fant 213	0.60	1.9 cd	0.9 c	197	99
IR4595-4-1-15	0.56	0.1 g	0.6 d	167	104
Pa Bathurst 32A	0.59	2.1 bc	0.6 d	180	98
Pokkali	0.75	0.7 fg	0.2 i	141	107
Moderate tolerance					
Improved Mashuri	0.52	0.8 f	0.5 de	174	92
CP4	0.49	2.7 ab	0.5 def	197	94
ROK5	0.54	2.7 ab	0.4 fgh	147	80
BD2	0.52	2.8 a	0.4 fgh	147	98
Low tolerance					
ROK10	0.39	2.6 ab	1.1 ab	197	95
BR51-49-6	0.38	1.2 ef	0.5 efg	164	81
BG90-2	0.31	0.9 ef	0.3 fgh	164	91
BG11-11	0.37	0.8 ef	0.3 hi	163	94
Djabon	0.33	1.4 de	0.3 hi	168	96
Bali Grodak	0.32	1.3 ef	0.3 hi	160	86
SE = 0.16					
CV (%)		16.8	12.7		

^aIn a column, values followed by identical letters are not significantly different from each other at the 5% level.

way to increase production at Rokupr during 1982-83.

In the ratoon study, 16 varieties produced grain (see table). The Pa Foday Yoreh 260 ratoon yield was 64.4% of the first crop yield. Other varieties that performed fairly well were ROK10, Pa Merr 108A, Pa Fant 213, IR4594-4-1-15, Pa Bathurst 32A, improved Mashuri, CP4, and BR51-49-6. Some varieties with low tolerance for salinity, such as ROK10, did fairly well because the ratoon crop matured before high soil salinity developed.

In the second crop study, only Pokkali was harvested, with 246 kg/ha grain yield. This highly salt-tolerant variety matured earlier than the other varieties, before the development of very high salt levels. The varieties which flowered late Apr to early May had empty spikelets. Average electrical conductivity during this period ranged from 15 to 18 mmho/cm for floodwater and 11 to 13 mmho/cm for topsoil.

Ratoon growth averaged 90 d. Photoperiod-sensitive Pa Merr 108A produced a ratoon crop in 94 d. This means that long-duration photoperiod-sensitive varieties harvested in Dec will produce a second ratoon crop in mid-March, much earlier than the normal second crop and well before the development of very high soil salinity. With the ratoon crop, land preparation, raising of seedlings, and transplanting are eliminated. □

Effect of time of lodging on rice productivity

B. Roy and J. N. Jha, *Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna, Bihar, India*

In Bihar, rain between the last week of Sep and the first week of Oct helps boost rice productivity. But, when this rain is accompanied by gusty wind, crops lodge. In 1985, rain during the